

Compliance with Girls' Power Initiative (GPI) Campaign against Domestic Violence among Female Residents of Cross River State

Njah Bassey, PhD

Department of Mass Communication

University of Cross River State

njahbasseyetta@unicross.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study sought to examine the compliance with Girls' Power Initiative (GPI) campaign against domestic violence among female residents of Cross River State between 2018 and 2020. Bandura's Social Learning theory and the Lenski's Social Inconsistency theory provided the theoretical framework. To address the research objectives, the study adopted the survey research design. The population for the study comprised female residents of Calabar within the age of 19 and 49. The Krejcie & Morgan formula was used in drawing a sample for the survey, giving a total of 384 respondents representing 99% of the study population for the questionnaire administration. In-depth interviews were conducted on 4 principal staff of GPI, Calabar Office. The descriptive analysis was used to analyze the quantitative data while the Constant Comparative Technique was used to analyze the qualitative data. Thereafter, both data were integrated and transformed for comparison. The findings reveal high compliance to GPI campaign on domestic violence among female residents of Cross River State as 381(99.48%) of the respondents have seen or heard of the campaign; 379 (98.96%) were open to receive the campaign messages. Women and girls' level of understanding of the campaign messages was overwhelming as 379(98.96%) of the respondents demonstrated their comprehension of the campaign's overall objective of curbing the spread of domestic violence against women and girls in Cross River State. The study concludes that the GPI campaign incorporated effective SBCC communication strategies, socio-ecological model as well as the monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Based on these findings, the study suggests a deeper exploration of formative research, as well as monitoring and evaluation mechanisms towards the sustainability of more participatory and people-centred communication strategies capable of ensuring appreciable impact in behaviour change interventions.

Keywords: Assessment, GPI, Campaign, Domestic Violence, Cross River State.

Introduction

Domestic violence is one of the major social health concerns across the world. The negative impact of this phenomenon affects all, no matter their social, racial, economic, educational, or religious backgrounds. All sectors of human society experience domestic violence in different ways, often resulting in physical and emotional injuries and even deaths, in some extreme cases.

Daily media reports on this issue often reveal that even the most successful and accomplished members of the society get entangled in this web, irrespective of their social status.

Men and women of all religious and cultural backgrounds, educated or illiterate, career or full-time spouses, married or singles suffer from this social health issue. Both those involved in heterosexual and homosexual relationships get affected by domestic violence. The fallacy that domestic violence is primarily committed by men in the society is erroneous as reports according to Dryden-Edwards (n.d.) indicate that over 800,000 men and teenage males are victims of intimate partner abuse globally. But the focus of this study is limited to domestic violence against women and teenage girls as the statistics about them continue to mount.

Domestic violence is known and addressed differently. Depending on the angle from which it is seen, it simply refers to a form of behaviour relating to the maltreatment of one partner by another in close relationships like marriage, cohabitation, dating, or within the family. Domestic violence can take many different forms, including physical aggression or assault (hitting, kicking, biting, shoving, restraining, slapping, throwing objects, battery), or threats thereof; sexual abuse; emotional abuse; controlling or domineering; intimidation; stalking; passive or covert abuse; and economic deprivation (Siemieniuk, Krentz, Gish & Gill, 2018). It involves verbal or psychological abuse, threats, use of force, or covert sexual assault by a spouse, family member, or other person. In the past, the issue of domestic violence was strictly associated with tangible acts of aggression and perpetrators were subjected to some legal sanctions. However, in recent times, it entails covert sexual assault, use of force, threats, verbal or psychological abuse by a spouse, family member, or other individual.

From the late 1970s, the issue of domestic violence has witnessed a dramatic increase both in scholarly and public attention to the study of the phenomenon. This is because the issue of domestic violence against women and girls has increased significantly as data according to the United Nations (UN) Women (2020) indicate that globally, 35 per cent of women have experienced one form of violence or another - physically, sexually, mentally, financially or otherwise. The enormity of domestic violence against women and teenage girls is prevalent in Nigeria and the magnitude of this problem is often underestimated due to the unavailability of studies that can help uncover its occurrence across various ethnic groups and socio-economic strata in the country. Furthermore, according to Broom (2020), 50,000 women are murdered each year by persons they know and should be able to trust. This number comes from the most recent UN statistics, which show that 137 women are killed every day by partners or family members worldwide.

Data obtained in a study conducted by the UN Women (2018) reveal that Nigeria has about 22.3% cases of Lifetime Physical and/or Sexual Intimate Partner Violence; 13.8% of Physical and/or Sexual Intimate Partner Violence within 2019; 43.4% of Child Marriage; and 19.5% cases of Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting. These results indicate a high prevalence of the issue in the country. The study further projects the picture of the problem across various socioeconomic strata in the Nigerian society, without limiting it to or giving it any particular coloration - tribal, cultural or religious. Hence, this report obviates the need for more studies to be designed to accommodate the multi-ethnic character of the Nigerian population consisting of well over three hundred different ethnic groups, in order to understand in-depth, the peculiar situation of this environment regarding domestic violence against women as it may be influenced by cultural and religious practices.

Communication is as old as mankind but continues to be pivotal and critical to all human activities, serving as the tool for social and grassroots mobilization, social change and community development. The pattern of communication of any society is an integral part of its total culture and can be interpreted in light of the context of its social structures, organizations and institutions. To successfully drive community development and social change in any given society, communication is considered a key determining factor as it helps to change people's worldviews and moral principles, making them more receptive to organic development and evolution and more adaptable. A number of responsibilities are usually assigned to communication in achieving certain development goals within societies. Consequently, policy makers, governments, civil societies, development agents and donor agencies and even those working in the private sector continuously acknowledge the role of communication in achieving their development goals and objectives.

Communication is relevant in changing knowledge and attitudes, thus improving positive social behaviours. Therefore, for innovations to gain widespread public adoption, communication is heavily relied upon to mobilize people for action towards the desired social change. Usually, development campaigns adopt communication channels and strategies to advocate and mobilize public participation towards achieving their desired goals. Knowledge built through advocacy and social mobilization helps the public to form opinions, frame their thoughts and portray the right attitude, react appropriately and respond accordingly to the demands as well as the yearnings of the development campaigners. This simply involves bringing people together to find shared or common understanding which can easily lead to a collective action for positive change in the society.

There is a growing prominence attached to participatory (horizontal) development communication. This is due to its involvement of the various stakeholders usually brought together for the purpose of dialogue and wide consultation, supporting the adoption of the bottom-up community media. The bottom-up approach helps in creating a conducive atmosphere where citizens define their development agenda, giving it meaning and claiming their citizenship. Furthermore, this form of communication guarantees the people the opportunity to be heard by helping them reshape both their social and cultural norms and boundaries that corroborate their knowledge and power relations with people both within and outside their immediate environment. Therefore, the relevance of mass communication to social and behaviour change cannot be overemphasized as both concepts have proven themselves useful, not only in the promotion of pre-determined social reforms, but also in trust building between development agents and the citizens. Participatory development has appeared to present some greater spirit that contributes to local reforms and sustainable change and development across all levels of society.

The concept of communication in its simplest meaning actually involves the sharing or exchange of data between a sender (the source) and a receiver (the destination). Ashong (1999) succinctly explains the essence of communication by referring to it as the sharing of meaning or producing mutual understanding. "And the objective of persons or groups engaged in communication usually is to achieve either what Newcomb calls "co-orientation" towards an object, idea or issue; or what Kincaid (1979) and Unoh (1987) cited in Ashong (2021, p.19) refer to as "convergence of opinion".

Statement of the Problem

As is customary in Nigeria and many other African nations, hitting spouse and kids is commonly accepted as a form of punishment (UNICEF, 2001). Although this phenomenon is generally frowned at in the Western World, some developing countries like the United Arab Emirate (UAE) still support it. This is evident in their 2010 Supreme Court ruling which gave the man the permission to ‘physically discipline’ his wife and children, provided he does not cause any physical injuries on them (Adebayo, 2014). In recent times, a woman’s refusal to yield to her partner's desires has become the most common justification for perpetration of these nefarious acts. It is further reinforced by cultures that see women as subordinates in the society, thereby causing men to arrogate excess powers to themselves.

What seems to reinforce the perpetration of domestic violence in Nigeria as in other countries around the world is the conspiracy of silence between the victims and the perpetrators. This trend further supports the stigma that the society usually associates with the victims without condemning the perpetrators. This has further worsened the situation, thereby reducing it to the private sphere and shielding it from public scrutiny.

One in three women worldwide are said to have experienced physical or sexual intimate relationship violence or non-partner sexual violence at some point in their lives. In Nigeria, 30% of women and girls between the ages of 15 and 49 are said to have suffered sexual abuse, mirroring these statistics (Centre for the Study of Economies of Africa (CSEA),2023).

Governments at all levels have made significant progress in tackling domestic violence prevention and response initiatives through their Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs), as well as civil society groups and NGOs. Despite these attempts, the issue has persisted as being deeply ingrained in our culture, particularly in light of the COVID-19 pandemic's role in bringing the scale of the issue into focus. Similarly, some notable Nigerian organizations such as *Stand To End Rape* (STER); *The Mirable Centre*; *Hands Off Initiative*; *WineandwhineNG*; *Women At Risk International Foundation* (WARIF); and the *Girls’ Power Initiative* (GPI) have made significant impacts across the country on issues mostly related to sexual violence against women. These organizations are assisting to create advocacy against domestic violence, thereby serving as Sexual Assault Referral Centres, providing psychosocial services and prevention mechanisms to support the victims and survivors. In addition, the UN has designated November 25 as the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women each year.

The GPI’s campaigns against domestic violence have been aimed at reducing the conspiracy of silence that is commonly observed between the victims and the perpetrators of this social vice, thus tending to assist the victims to identify certain behaviours that infringe on their wellbeing, thereby providing them with the necessary support to get justice.

This study, therefore, aimed to carry out an assessment of the GPI’s campaign on domestic violence against women and girls in Cross River State in the 2018 to 2020 fiscal years. Thus, the problem investigated was: What was the communication strategy of GPI’s campaign against domestic violence and how did it help to shape the response of both victims and women generally to the phenomenon in Cross River State?

Objectives of the Study

This study sought to:

- i. examine the communication strategy of GPI's campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State between 2018 and 2020; And
- ii. assess women's level of understanding of the campaign messages against domestic violence in Cross River State.

Research Questions

- i. What was the communication strategy of GPI's campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State between 2018 and 2020?
- ii. What was Cross River State women's level of understanding of the campaign messages against domestic violence?

The Concept of Domestic Violence against Women and Girls: An Overview

Domestic violence is a problem, especially when it affects women and girls, and it is an example of historically unfair power relationships between men and women. Due to the pervasiveness of this problem in our culture, men dominate and discriminate against women, which prevents women from achieving complete equality (UN, 1993). Domestic abuse against women has sparked outrage all around the world. This is not to suggest that there are not any incidents of males who have been involved in domestic disputes with their intimate partners that have been documented. As an illustration, consider the recent murder of Biliyaminu Bello by his wife Miriam Sander (Oguntola & Ibeh, 2023).

However, there exist numerous reports indicating that women predominantly suffer domestic violence more than their male counterparts. Nigerians would not soon forget the heartbreaking tale of Osinachi Nwachukwu, a well-known gospel singer, who passed away after reportedly experiencing spousal violence from her husband Peter Nwachukwu. According to reports, the accused perpetrator of this despicable act kicked the woman in the chest, causing a blood clot that ultimately killed her. Recall also the case of one David Idibie, a resident of Ajah area of Lagos who was arrested by the Lagos State Police Command for killing his 42-year-old wife, Juliana Idibie.

The same thing happened in April 2020 when Anulika Uguru who passed away in Ekeru-Inyimaegu in the Izzi Local Government Area of Ebonyi State as a result of reports of domestic violence and battery by her husband. There is also the case of one Abimbola Martins-Ogbonna, who was alleged to have died in a fire incident in her residence in Ajah. But other reports indicated that the victim had made a formal report to the Lagos State Domestic and Sexual Violence Agency (DSVA) about the series of violent attacks she suffered from her husband, Ikechukwu Ogbonna, a popular car dealer in the state. Similarly, a 48-year-old businesswoman, Ijeoma Phillis Chiboli was also reportedly murdered by Tochukwu Christian Edeh, her 31-year-old intimate partner due to a failed business transaction. On July 20th, 2023, a 34-year-old Esther Ndarake was allegedly murdered by one Nkereuwem Etuk, her 54-year-old lover during an argument at Abasi Obori Street, Calabar South LGA of Cross River State.

The issue of domestic violence is prevalent and occurs virtually in every society in varying degrees. According to Bricknell (2019), domestic and family violence has become a problem of epidemic proportions in society. It is one issue that has always made headlines in major newspapers

and magazines across the world as its impact is highly pervasive and comes in various forms - physically, sexually, emotionally, economically and psychologically. Sadly, it occurs regularly behind closed doors in the home, a place that should be a safe and supportive environment. These happen despite efforts by state and national legislators to properly define and penalize perpetrators of domestic violence.

Understanding Risk Factors for Domestic Violence Using the Ecological Model

Recent global happenings have caused a paradigm shift in the way and manner in which social and behaviour change programmes were organized. The growing consensus is that campaigns for the prevention of behaviour-related issues such as domestic violence have ceased to be the sole preserve of experts and professionals. As new developments occur, new dynamics and strategies are designed to address the issue at hand. To achieve positive results, such campaigns require the efforts of entire communities, including policy makers, violence against women educators and practitioners, behaviour change experts and social marketers (Alexander-Scott, Bell & Holden, 2016).

One method of engaging communities is through social and behaviour change communication (SBCC) interventions that target a wide audience over a certain time period and employ the media, message, interactive communication, and other communication activities to achieve specific results. As there is some evidence to show that mass media campaigns, without interpersonal or environmental interventions, are unlikely to induce behaviour change, such campaigns aim to mold behaviour toward desirable societal outcomes.

The majority of African family systems, including those in Nigeria, are patriarchal and assign males leadership positions while placing females in a submissive position. In Nigeria's multiethnic society, there are three main ethnic groupings (Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba), each one having their peculiar cultural practices. The only similarity they share in common is that these ethnic groups and the rest of the minority groups only give women in the society a second fiddle position to occupy, irrespective of their background, exposure, educational attainment, or experiences. The intrinsic supremacy of men over women is embraced by Nigerian traditional and cultural customs. Even Nigeria's two main religions, Christianity and Islam, have not been able to free Nigerian women from the gender discrimination that cultural norms have placed on them.

The risk factors for perpetration of violence against women and/or girls are interlinked to each other. Domestic violence experts have submitted that although these factors are contributing to the perpetration of this phenomenon, they might not be the direct causes of domestic violence in most cases. Therefore, it is necessary for one to know the multilevel factors that can help researchers and behaviour change agents in identifying available opportunities for the prevention of domestic violence in the society. According to the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2021) and the National Centre for Injury Prevention and Control, Division of Violence Prevention (2021), individual, interpersonal, social, and environmental variables all work together to

increase the risk of committing domestic violence.

Ecological Model for Understanding Domestic Violence with Added Risk Factors (NCIPC, 2021) Figure 1.

Note, the ecological model's above division of the risk variables for domestic violence into four categories does not make them independent of each other. Practically, the impacts caused by these risk factors are interwoven and cannot be separated from each other. At one point or the other, these risk factors have the tendencies of overlapping each other (Bakare *et al*, 2010, p. 10).

Historical Background of Girls' Power Initiative (GPI), Nigeria

GPI, the center of this study, is a feminist, youth development, non-profit organization founded in 1993 with the goal of influencing girls' socialization in order to realize a future in which women are recognized as important players in Nigeria, as seen by the organization's slogan, "Towards an Empowered Womanhood." Their primary goal is to advance children's rights, particularly those of girls, and to encourage involvement in development through programmes that are empowerment-focused, grounded in research, and education. The founders, having worked in the women's movement, observed the complacency of women in demanding and realizing their human rights. They therefore, decided to work with girls to 'catch them young' with a view to equipping them with knowledge and leadership skills from a gender and human rights perspective for the achievement of gender equality.

Activities with the registered girls commenced in July 1994 in Cross River and Edo States with new registration done yearly. Graduates from the 3-year safe space comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) programme automatically became members of the GPI Alumnae Association (GAA). The activities expanded to Akwa Ibom and Delta States in 2002, commenced in 2018 in Bayelsa and the National Liaison Office, Abuja opened in 2017. They began operation in 1994 with their daughters and friends from their communities of residence in Edo and Cross River states, respectively. Further interactions with the girls showed that they were interested in knowing more about sexuality issues and relationships – this helped structure the organization's 3-year education programme as it evolved from a gender and leadership-focused training programme to a CSE programme with gender and human rights as cross cutting issues.

The GPI in her nearly 30 years of existence has successfully carried out 67 campaigns in the following areas:

- i. Safeguarding young girls and female children.
- ii. Better understanding of issues related to teenage sexuality to lessen susceptibility and challenges with reproductive health among young girls.
- iii. Breaking down obstacles related to gender and human rights that prevent girls and young women from being the greatest versions of themselves.
- iv. Developing leadership and entrepreneurial abilities with the goal of completely eliminating gender discrimination, which limits the ability of girls and young women to further their intellectual and economic growth.

The successful implementation of these campaigns was attributed to the concerted efforts of the management and staff as well as their numerous donors and sponsors especially, the *UN Women, International Women's Health Coalition, UNICEF, UNESCO, WHO*, the Federal and State governments through the Ministries of Health, Social Welfare and the Child's Rights agencies. Through effective communication interventions, intense and core communication messages were designed and implemented to address the abuse of rights of women and young females within and outside their areas of operation. The intervention messages were designed, using different communication strategies and this helped to curb the widespread gender discrimination that was witnessed at the time. Despite reports of clashes in certain areas, the issue of women's abuse was declining because of persistent lobbying, social and community mobilization, and social and behaviour change communication (SBCC) initiatives.

In spite of these efforts, not much success has been made in the organization's attempt to curb the pervasiveness of domestic violence in the state, especially against women and girls. There still exists vast evidence of the occurrence of this public health menace in various communities across the state. Unfortunately, some of these cases go unreported due to the challenges faced in accessing affordable quality support services. In many cases, women and girls face challenges in accessing support services due to socio-cultural norms and fear of stigma and discrimination which has led to the significant under-reporting of cases of domestic violence, such that scanty existing data only represent the tip of the iceberg. According to GPI's research on the empowerment of girls and young women, the situation is attributable to a lack of political will at all levels of decision-making to address issues affecting women and young females, particularly patriarchal values and gender stereotypes; harmful practices against girls and young females; community apathy and neglect of girls and young females; and a lack of a supportive environment, particularly at the public level.

Methodology

This study adopted the survey research technique so as to examine the GPI's campaign messages against domestic violence in Cross River State. **To do this effectively, the researcher analyzed** the said campaign with particular emphasis on the communication strategy to assist the researcher in determining the level of female residents' exposure to the campaign messages, their level of understanding of the messages and how these helped them to identify behaviours that represent domestic violence.

The population of this study was drawn from women and girls between the age range of 19 and 49 in Cross River State as well as some principal staff officers of GPI, Calabar Office. This purposive choice of women and girls in the state as the population for this study stems from the fact that they were the prime survivors of domestic abuses and the target beneficiaries of GPI campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State. The choice of staff of GPI, Calabar

Office was due to their roles as the major planners and implementers of the campaigns, with support and sponsorship from *UN Women, International Women’s Health Coalition, UNICEF, UNESCO, WHO*, the Federal and State governments through the Ministries of Health, Social Welfare and the Child Right agencies.

The population figure of women and girls in Cross River State currently stands at 1,421,021 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021), while the population of staff of GPI, Calabar stands at 26 (<https://gpicalabar.org/our-staff/>). Due to the vastness of Cross River State, it was challenging to study the entire population. Consequently, a subset of the population was chosen so that characteristics displayed by the larger subset sampled for this study were acknowledged as being a good representation of the entire population of the state, thereby allowing for the generalization of the research findings. Therefore, a sample size of 384 was therefore used for the study.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

RQ1: What was the communication strategy of GPI campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State between 2018 and 2020?

Table 1: Responses on the Source of GPI Campaigns Messages in CRS

Source of Campaign Messages.	F (%)					Decision
	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	
Mass media	291(75.98)	70(18.28)	12(3.13)	10(2.61)	3.68	Accepted
Town-hall meetings	240(62.66)	129(33.68)	12(3.13)	2(0.52)	3.58	Accepted
IPC/Face-to-face meetings	223(60.84)	103(26.89)	37(9.66)	10(2.61)	3.56	Accepted
Local Rallies	237(61.88)	126(32.90)	15(3.92)	5(1.31)	3.55	Accepted
Sponsorship of local events	263(68.67)	115(30.03)	3(0.78)	2(0.52)	3.67	Accepted
Folk dramas	259(67.62)	114(29.77)	8(2.09)	2(0.52)	3.64	Accepted

In line with the depth of the statement of the problem guiding this study, the necessity to ascertain the communication strategy of GPI campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State between 2018 and 2020 was vital for several reasons. Most importantly, to enhance a thorough knowledge of the dynamics of the GPI campaign and shed light on the specific strategies and methods employed to combat the region's deeply entrenched culture of domestic violence. Addressing social problems such as domestic violence is often not straightforward due to the complex cultural and societal factors underpinning them. Consequently, the necessity of having a detailed study of the communication strategy of GPI campaign against domestic violence offered a wealth of insights into the practicalities of executing an effective behaviour-based intervention such as this within Cross River State's cultural and social confines.

The core objective of public awareness campaigns is to sensitize the public on some specific issues, and in this case, domestic violence. Such interventions help in highlighting such

issues by bringing them to the foreground of public dialogue. Such efforts help to alter social knowledge of the existence of the issue, thereby encouraging people to refrain from the action. The purpose of public awareness interventions against domestic violence is to sensitize the public on the prevalence of the abuse and support social actions that discourages the act. Consequently, victims of domestic violence can therefore be alerted on the options and resources available for them to them to explore (National Resource Centre for Domestic Violence, 2021).

In answering this research question, the analysis of data in Table 1 provides adequate information into the communication strategy of the GPI campaign against domestic violence in Cross River State. Similarly, the communication strategy of GPI campaign detailed in the interview responses gathered and synthesized in this study are invaluable. Data in Table 1 reveal that majority of the study participants got the campaign messages either through the mass media or town hall meetings, IPC/face-to-face meetings, local rallies, sponsorship of local events and folk dramas. The weighted mean for these communication strategies adopted by GPI during their campaign ranked between 3.55 and 3.68, symbolizing that majority of the respondents agreed to the effectiveness of these means in creating adequate awareness for the campaign.

Corroborating the above findings, the interview sessions further disclosed that GPI consolidated on the knowledge built and the awareness created about their campaign by disclosing that the campaign commenced with advocacy visits to the relevant political, community and religious stakeholders to rally support and ensure their commitment to the campaign. This effort supports the submission of Khan, Nawaz and Khan (2016) that positive ‘engagement of actors’ on both sides in policy discourse and decision-making process is a hallmark of democratic nation as more interactions generate more information and feedback from diverse stakeholders, thus dispelling the myths about the sensitivity of the subject as well as enhancing the chances for stronger support for policies.

Furthermore, the campaign also adopted the support media, distance learning and other SBCC strategies to reach out to and gain public support for the campaign. These community-integrated approaches successfully created valuable relationships with the stakeholders and at-risk families within the communities, thereby providing the mechanisms that allowed for effective communication and collaboration. A comprehensive community-integrated and community mobilization effort also helped to provide local endorsement of the intervention and removed barriers that would have affected the programme implementation.

Effective public information as well as awareness strategies about domestic violence as a social crime against women and girls can help change public attitudes and norms. This supports the position of Moreno-Martin, Alvarez, Alonso & Villanueva (2020), that a comprehensive goal-oriented SBCC intervention often requires the combination of mass media channels, townhall meetings, and other community-based approaches such as town meetings and community theatres. These assists campaign organizers in meeting their goals by raising adequate awareness about the issue, presenting it as a social health danger, ensuring accurate disseminate of information, dispelling misconceptions and myths about domestic violence and changing public opinion.

The outcomes of this study reveal that infusing the residents of CRS with enormous communication activities in view of keeping them abreast of the latest developments about the GPI campaign on domestic violence is a clear revelation that communication is pivotal to the success of interventions. This also indicates that communication is a vital tool upon which people share information with one another to enhance understanding. Beyond its persuading function, communication also helps in furnishing people with adequate information to sell the campaign objectives to those concerned. Effective communication empowers people to perform at their best

and minimizes misunderstandings. It also helps in driving organizational success. Campaign planners and implementers can therefore prioritize the use of clear language which helps in building strong and cohesive teams that can leverage on explicit communication and mutual understanding.

Finally, the findings of this study are in tune with the tenets of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory of Everett Rogers (1942) which submits that communication of novel projects and innovations tends to help people as members of a social system to accept and adopt new ideas, innovations, new attitudes and technologies that can help their survival or advance their social existence.

RQ2: What was women’s level of understanding of the campaign’s messages against domestic violence?

Table 2: Respondents’ Understanding of GPI Campaign Messages in Cross River State.

Understanding of Campaign Messages	F (%)					
	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Decision
Curbing domestic violence.	278(72.60)	101(26.37)	3(0.78)	1(0.26)	3.72	Accepted
Restraining conspiracy of silence.	274(71.54)	100(26.11)	7(1.83)	2(0.52)	3.69	Accepted
Destroying our cultural values.	1(0.26)	1(0.26)	15(3.92)	366(95.56)	1.05	Rejected
Making women and girls disobedient.	3(0.78)	2(0.52)	57(14.90)	321(83.81)	1.18	Rejected
Promoting feminism.	11(2.87)	4(1.04)	169(44.13)	199(51.96)	1.55	Rejected
Instigating women against men.	4(1.04)	4(1.04)	109(28.46)	266(69.45)	1.34	Rejected

When assessing the effectiveness of any campaign, the level of understanding of its messages by its intended audience is a critical factor. As highlighted in the previous response, if a significant comprehension gap is found, it implies a need for reformulating the campaign's strategy. The answer to the above research question is detailed in the analysis of data displayed in Table 2.

From the data, majority (379, i.e., 98.96%) of the study participants indicated that the GPI intervention was aimed at curbing the spread of domestic violence against women and girls in CRS. The data also revealed that the majority (374, i.e., 97.65%) of the respondents understood that the intervention was aimed at curbing the culture of conspiracy of silence prevalent among victims and perpetrators of domestic violence within the state. This is confirmed through the interview data which revealed that most of the beneficiaries still remembered the campaign slogan until the post-campaign monitoring and evaluation (M&E) period.

Summing up the inferences drawn from the two data sets indicates that there was increased understanding of the campaign messages among the respondents. The stratification of the target audience, translation of the campaign messages, and the use of local interpreters served as reinforcement to their understanding of the messages. The campaign posters and fliers prepared in their local dialects also supported this effort.

However, despite the largely positive impact of the campaign, a closer look at the data reveals certain areas that warrant further attention. Although most respondents were satisfied with the campaign's objectives, organization and clarity of messages, a minute percentage (5, i.e., 1.3%) expressed displeasure. This may indicate that the campaign's communication strategies require further refinement which might involve the spreading of more evidence-based information. Furthermore, it is necessary to examine whether the campaign messages are culturally sensitive, devoid of jargon and ambiguity, and delivered in local channels and in languages that all women can understand is crucial. Also, the inclusivity of the campaign should be a significant consideration in its design and delivery, as its effectiveness is contingent upon reaching all women, irrespective of their educational, socio-economic, or cultural backgrounds and getting them to be at par with others (Trujillo, Obando & Trujillo, 2019).

The high degree of audience recall of the campaign messages, in spite of its not-for-profit approach, was a pivotal testament to its deep understanding in the public space. Data also bespoke of the presence of a significant correlation between women's exposure to GPI campaign messages and their understanding of domestic violence. This is in accordance with the position of McGuire (2001) communication/persuasion matrix which submits that an important conceptual foundation for assessing health communication programmes (a wide reach of the target audience and proper understanding of the communicated messages) are essential requirements for evaluating communication effectiveness.

The above outcomes are at variance with the findings of the study conducted by Viswanath & Ackerson (2011) which submitted that the ability of audience understanding and recall of campaign messages in health communication interventions is dependent on the living conditions of the beneficiaries at a time. To Viswanath and Race, those under comfortable conditions are more likely to be reached by the campaigners and their level of receptiveness and understanding higher compared with others. This study demonstrates that rather than their living conditions, factors that could possibly affect the individual's ability to receive, understand and make meaning of campaign messages are dependent on parenting and variables like parental attitudes, self-assuredness, behaviour problems, and violent progenitorship or upbringing. Therefore, knowing what messages resonate with the target demographic and facilitate understanding can guide policy recommendations for domestic violence prevention programmes.

It is equally critical to delve deeper into the reasons for the uncertainty and disagreement of a minor percentage of respondents about the campaign's effectiveness. Is it the mode of delivery, geographic reach, cultural sensitivity, or the movement's inability to address specific, localized issues related to domestic violence that led to their skepticism or indifference? Addressing these concerns can help fine-tune the campaign and improve its efficacy (Gracia-Moreno, Zimmerman, Morris-Gehring, Heise, Amin, Abrahams, Montoya, Bhate-Deosthali, Kilonzo, & Watts (2015)). The data paints a compelling picture of the GPI's domestic violence campaign's triumph, indicating its successful penetration and positive impact on societal perceptions of domestic violence. However, an in-depth analysis also reveals gaps and

shortcomings that must be addressed to make these campaigns more inclusive, far-reaching, and effective.

It must be noted that reaching the goal of any effective health communication intervention requires the building of the campaign around clear messages capable of stating the problem to be addressed, solutions proposed (in line with the campaign's objectives), and audience's understanding of the campaign messages. For such messages to be considered effective, they must capture the attention of the target audience without requiring any additional explanation. Above all, such messages must be understood by the campaign beneficiaries (UN Women, 2012).

Conclusion

The campaign's educational and transformative power has proven instrumental in challenging traditionally ingrained perceptions about domestic violence. The data reveal an overwhelmingly positive shift in attitudes following the campaign, indicating that the campaign changed their perspective on domestic violence.

Furthermore, the findings affirm the critical role of social learning in shaping attitudes and behaviours. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) is a cogent explanatory framework for the study outcome, suggesting that behaviours and attitudes, even those rooted in longstanding societal norms, can be significantly altered through exposure to new perspectives. Nevertheless, while this study signals a positive trend in women's attitudes, it simultaneously casts a spotlight on the potential implications of Status Inconsistency Theory. It should be noted that women's empowerment can create a perceived inconsistency for men accustomed to traditional gender hierarchies (Lenski, 1954). Thus, the campaigns' effectiveness in driving societal change might not be utterly discernible without considering the potential escalation of violence resulting from status inconsistencies.

On the policy front, the evidence could stimulate discourse around the pressing need for governments and policy-makers to invest in initiatives that educate and shift societal norms actively. Consideration should be given to how policy changes can foster an environment where these campaigns have the broadest reach and the most substantial impact. While the original discussion is comprehensive, there are opportunities to expand upon the interplay of theoretical perspectives, practical applications, and policy implications arising from the study findings. A fuller understanding of the issue can be achieved through an integrative and critical lens.

Recommendations

On the basis of the study's findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Future behaviour change campaigns by GPI requiring shifts in attitudes and perceptions should accord deeper exploration into discerning the more appropriate communication strategies capable of ensuring appreciable impact.
- ii. GPI should take advantage of the women empowerment brought about by the campaign to delve into the specifics of the empowerment, including the role of community support, the effectiveness of legal aids, and availability of safe spaces. These will illuminate how to empower women best to resist domestic violence against them.

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